

Original Article

BUSINESS EDUCATORS' PERCEPTION OF SEARCH ENGINE AND E-MAIL MARKETING SKILLS REQUIRED FOR SELF-EMPLOYMENT BY BUSINESS EDUCATION STUDENTS IN SOUTH-SOUTH, NIGERIA

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DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17492487>

Abstract

The study determine the perception of Business Educators on search engine and email marketing skills required by Business Education students in universities in South-South, Nigeria for self-employment upon graduation. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested. Descriptive survey research design was adopted in the study. The population of this study consisted of 199 Business Educators (102 males and 97 females) in 12 public universities in South-South, Nigeria. The entire population was studied without sampling because the size was manageable. A four-point rating scale questionnaire titled "Digital Marketing Skill Assessment Questionnaire" (DMSAQ) and containing 10 items in two clusters according to the research questions was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts with overall reliability coefficient value of 0.83. Data collected relating to the research questions were analysed using Cronbach Alpha to determine its reliability. Data for the study were collected by the researchers through Google form and direct contact with the respondents with the help of four research assistants who were guided on the process. Out of 199 copies of the instrument administered, 189 copies representing 95% were returned and used for data analysis. Mean was used to answer the research questions. Standard deviation was used to determine the closeness of the responses of the respondents. The null hypotheses were tested using t-test analysis at .05 level of significance. Findings of the study revealed that Business Educators perceived that search engine marketing skills and email marketing skills are required in Business Education in South-South, Nigeria for self-employment. Based on the findings, it was concluded that if Business Education students in the area are not adequately equipped with skills in the two areas, it will be difficult for them to succeed in self-employment in the increasingly competitive and technology-driven economy. It was, therefore, recommended among others that Business Educators should regularly attend short training, conferences, and workshops on emerging digital marketing tools and techniques to stay current and effectively teach these skills and that management of universities should sponsor their Business Educators to these professional development programmes and partner with digital marketing firms and professionals to provide real-world exposure, internships, and hands-on experiences to Business Education students to equip them for self-employment.

Keywords: Business educators, Business education, Search engine marketing, Email marketing, Self-employment..

Introduction

A Business educator is a professionally trained educator of business courses who is competent in teaching all the components of the business education programme. Fisher (2023) stated that a business educator is a professional who specializes in teaching and training individuals in various aspects of business. Ekanem, Agba and Eminue (2017), noted that business educators must be knowledgeable about the skills being taught and device means in the lesson to pass much of the work skills to the learners. According to Akpomi and Ikpesu (2021), the changing business world places much demand on business education providers to prepare value adding business leaders, managers, employees, entrepreneurs, producers and consumers who can fit perfectly into national and global economy. According to Osuala in Nwokike and Ezeabii (2017), business education courses must be handled by well trained and motivated persons with academic and professional competencies which will match the industrial expectations. The National Universities Commission has inherently incorporates entrepreneurial principles and digital marketing skills in the curriculum of business education, making them fundamental building blocks of business learning from the very beginning. Business educator as an individual plays an essential role in making Business education viable and visible in the university and beyond.

Business education is an educational programme that embraces basic education for teaching career, entrepreneurship, business understanding, office environment and vocational practices. Emeasoba and Nwatarali (2020) noted that business education programme in the university provides students with

needed competencies, skills, knowledge, understanding and attitude to perform as workers in industries, civil service and entrepreneurs. Olumese and Ediagbonya (2016) stated that business education is a vocational-oriented programme that exposes recipients to a number of specialized areas such as secretarial/office technology studies, business management, distributive education, ICT and accounting education. Edokpolor and Egbri (2017) averred that the actual goals of business education are to prepare students for specific career in office occupations; equip students with the requisite skills for job creation and entrepreneurship; and expose students with the knowledge about business, including a good blend of computer technology which incorporates information and communication technology (ICT). Furthermore, Enang (2016) explained that business education empowers students with desired knowledge, skills and values that would make them to be self-employed or employable by others. It is an education that equips students with employable skills thereby making them to be self-reliant.

Self-employment rate can be related to the stage of economic development through improvement in physical and communication infrastructures in the financial market. Self-employment is currently on the increase globally because it leads to reduction in graduate unemployment and other societal ills like youth restiveness and crime which are caused by poverty (Fatoki, 2015). Dabale and Masese (2015) analyzed self-employment in three dimensions; first the intention to become self-employed which depends on someone's level of tolerance for risk and independence which will likely determine, to a great extent, what they will achieve. The second is perceived ability, which means recognizing an opportunity and acting on it while the third is investing required resources by the individual and stakeholders. In recent years, the rise of digital

technologies has transformed the landscape of self-employment, providing new avenues for individuals to market their skills, reach customers, and build successful ventures. Effectiveness of digital marketing skills training program fosters employability and productivity (Abdullahi, Ojeleye, & Abdullahi, 2022). Digital marketing skills have become essential for individuals seeking to achieve success in self-employment. For Business Education students, the acquisition of digital marketing skills can be a crucial enabler of self-employment (Okoro & Emeasoba, 2025). Digital marketing encompasses a wide range of techniques, strategies and skills (Mohammed *et.al*, 2020), including search engine marketing and email marketing

Search Engine Marketing (SEM) is a digital marketing strategy used to gain website traffic and visibility through search engines like Google, Bing, and Yahoo. Topfloor Tech (2018) defined Search Engine Marketing as the process of increasing traffic and visibility of your website, product and services through a search engine. In same vein, Terrance, Shrivastave and Kumari (2017) opined that SEM is the marketing process with a goal of obtaining more visibility in search engine either by getting more free traffic or paid traffic. Standberry, (2019) noted that SEM can be used to get focused on the target market cost-effectively as the ads do not cost anything until someone clicks it. Since consumers are typing the search queries to find commercial information anyway, they are in an excellent position to receive marketing messages and unlike the other digital marketing methods. Search engine marketing is non-intrusive, which makes it a great and fast way to drive traffic to a website. Topfloor Tech also stated that Search Engine Marketing (SEM) incorporate search engine optimization (SEO) which adjust or rewrite the website content and site architecture in order to achieve higher page rank in Search engine result pages and enhance pay-per-click (PPC) listings. By

targeting relevant keywords and implementing best practices, self-employed individuals can use e-mail marketing to enhance their online discoverability and attract potential customers who are actively searching for their products or services.

Electronic mail marketing is an analogy of direct mail. E-mail is one of many online channels that can be used by companies to build and enhance their customer relationships (Boateng & Narteh, 2016). Chaffey and EllisChadwick, (2019) defined Email Marketing as an effective channel in marketing strategy not only as a tool to increase brand visibility and brand awareness but also has an excellent tool to help promote and sell. Marketers need to understand how email marketing can facilitate establishing strong long-term customer relationships and stand out from the crowd of competitors. Rosario (2021) also noted that e-mail Marketing helps to promote any business online by sending emails to current and future customers. E-mail marketing has over the past years shifted from a more profit-generating purpose to the additional intention of customer relationship building, engagement and long-term loyalty, also partly due to customers' increasing knowledge and influence (Zhang *et al.*, 2017). From a relationship marketing perspective, e-mail marketing can be positioned within the subject of online relationship marketing as a communication tool. E-mail marketing allows direct and targeted one-to-one communication between the business and the target individual. Moreover, due to the development of technology e-mail marketing has gained better opportunities to track and deliver more adapted and personalized email content which meet the customers' preferences (Heimbach et al., 2015; Mahmoud et al., 2019). Likewise, as a lead generation and nurturing tool, e-mail marketing is likely to provide companies with insights into customer interests, behaviour, and buying intentions (Todor, 2016). The characteristics of e-mail marketing as presented above underline the importance of e-mail

for both acquiring new customers and building personalised long-term relationships with existing ones. Hence, the use of e-mail marketing, in combination with Search Engine for marketing strategies, is considered to be an important aspect of integrated marketing communications. By understanding this fundamental concept of digital marketing and mastering these skills, Business Education students can develop the necessary competencies to effectively promote their services, attract clients, and manage the operational aspects of their self-employed endeavours.

Problem of the study

In an era marked by rapid digital transformation, the global workforce is increasingly driven by information and communication technologies (ICT), particularly digital marketing skills such as search engine marketing and email marketing. These skills have become indispensable for entrepreneurial success, especially among young graduates seeking self-employment. In Nigeria, where graduate unemployment continues to rise—particularly in the South-South region—the integration of practical digital marketing competencies into university curricula has become increasingly vital. However, Business Education programs have often failed to equip students with relevant, market-driven digital skills.

The problem addressed by this study is that, despite the significant potential of search engine and email marketing as cost-effective tools for small business growth and personal brand visibility, there is limited empirical data on how Business Educators perceive their relevance and applicability in equipping students for self-employment upon graduation. Business Educators play a critical role in shaping both curriculum content and student competence; thus, their perceptions can either drive or hinder adequate

emphasis on these essential digital skills within the program.

If educators undervalue or lack awareness of the relevance of these tools in preparing students for self-employment, graduates may lack the competencies needed to thrive as entrepreneurs in the digital economy. Therefore, this study seeks to determine the perceptions of Business Educators in universities in South-South Nigeria regarding the extent to which search engine and email marketing skills are required by Business Education students for self-employment upon graduation. The findings will provide empirical data to guide relevant stakeholders in taking informed actions to ensure that university Business Education graduates in the region are adequately equipped for success in self-employment.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was determine perception of Business Educators on the level at which:

1. Search engine marketing (SEM) skills are required by university Business Education students in South-South, Nigeria for self-employment.
2. Email marketing skills are required by university Business Education students in South-South, Nigeria for self-employment.

3. Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the perception of Business Educators on the level of search engine marketing (SEM) skills required by university Business Education students in South-South, Nigeria for self-employment?
2. What is the perception of Business Educators on the level of email marketing skills required by university Business Education students in South-South, Nigeria for self-employment?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.5 alpha level of significance:

H0₁: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female Business Educators on the level of search engine marketing (SEM) skills required by universities–Business Education students in South-South, Nigeria for self-employment.

H0₂: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female Business Educators on the level of email marketing skills required by universities–Business Education students in South-South, Nigeria for self-employment.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. This design was deemed suitable because it enabled the researcher to identify existing conditions, gather and analyse current data regarding Business Educators' perceptions while providing valuable data for informed decision-making. As Siedlecki (2020) explained, the primary objective of descriptive survey is to observe and describe individuals, events, or conditions in their natural state. The population of the study comprised all 199 Business Educators (102 males and 97 Females in all the 12 federal and state universities offering Business Education in South-south, Nigeria. The entire population was studied without sampling because the size was manageable. The instrument for data collection was a four-point rating scale questionnaire titled “Digital Marketing Skill Assessment Questionnaire” (DMSAQ) and containing 10 items in two clusters according to the research questions was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts two in Business Education and one from Measurement and Evaluation, all in College of Education, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Abia State. The reliability of the 20 instrument was established using the internal consistency method by administering it to 20 business educators in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State which is outside the South-South zone and not part of the study but with similar characteristics. The data collected

were analyzed using Cronbach Alpha and reliability coefficient values of 0.80 and 0.86 were obtained for the two clusters with an overall reliability coefficient value of 0.83. Data for the study were collected by the researchers through direct contact with the respondents with the help of four research assistants who were guided on the process. Copies of the instrument were distributed to the respondents during the first visit and they were given five days before the researchers and assistants revisited them to retrieve their responses. This was done to ensure a high response rate. Consequently, out 199 copies of the instrument distributed, 189 copies (representing 95%) were retrieved with an attrition of only 10 copies.

Data collected were analyzed using mean to answer the research questions and standard deviation to determine the homogeneity of the mean responses while t-test statistic was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The data analysis was done using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS). The decision rule for the research questions was based on the principle of real limits of the mean so that the researcher can get the actual response limit of the respondents or clear-cut decisions, objective decision-making, control over type 1 error rate among others: Very Highly Required (VHR) 3.50 - 4.0, Highly Required (HR) 2.50 - 3.49, Required (R) 1.50 - 2.49, Not Required (NR) 1.00 - 1.49. The null hypotheses were tested using t-test analysis at .05 level of significance and at the appropriate degree of freedom because the researcher used two groups. The decision rule for the hypotheses were that the null hypothesis was not rejected when calculated p-value is equal to or greater than 0.05 level of significance ($p > 0.05$) but was rejected when the calculated p-value is less than the level of significance ($p < 0.05$). These served as a criterion for making inferences for the data collected to enable the researcher provide answers for the research questions

raised and hypotheses formulated that are meant to guide the study.

RESULTS

Table 1: Respondents' mean ratings on the level of search engine marketing skills required by university Business Education students in South-South Nigeria for self-employment

S/N	Item Statements	Male Educators N ₁ =98		Female Educators N ₂ = 91		Remark	
		X ₁	SD ₁	X ₂	$\frac{X_1 + X_2}{2}$		
					2		SD ₂
1.	Ability to conduct keyword research using tools that will bring search result of interest	3.58	0.64	3.76	3.67	0.52	VHR
2.	Ability to use search engine tools to locate online resource	3.52	0.69	3.62	3.57	0.57	VHR
3.	Ability to identify which search engines is the related website you want your site to appear on	3.53	0.68	3.58	3.55	0.60	VHR
4.	Ability to optimize website content for search engine visibility	3.45	0.71	3.60	3.53	0.59	VHR
5.	Knowledge of search engine algorithms and ranking factors	3.43	0.79	3.43	3.43	0.72	HR
6.	Ability to identify consumers buying habits	3.51	0.69	3.67	3.59	0.56	VHR
7.	Ability to perform competitor analysis in search engine results	3.38	0.77	3.31	3.35	0.80	HR
8.	Ability to attract traffic online	3.31	0.75	3.46	3.39	0.62	HR
9.	Ability to apply search engine marketing (SEM) techniques for online visibility	3.35	0.86	3.45	3.40	0.70	HR
10.	Ability to manage pay-per-click (PPC) campaigns	3.23	0.90	3.21	3.22	0.85	HR
Cluster Mean		3.43	0.75	3.51	3.47	0.65	HR

Table 1 indicates the mean ratings of both male and female respondents for all the search engine skills range from 3.21 - 3.76 showing that the respondents perceived all the skills as required by their students. The cluster mean scores of the two groups are also above 2.50. This means that the business educators used in the study perceived search engine marketing

skills as required by university Business Education students in South-South, Nigeria for self-employment. Standard deviation values ranged between 0.52 and 0.90, indicating a relatively low dispersion and a high level of agreement among respondents.

Table 2: Summary of t-test results of difference between the mean ratings of male and female business educators on search engine skills required by university business education students for self-employment

Groups	N	X	SD	Df	t	P-value	Decision
Male Business Educators	98	3.43	0.75	187	0.79	0.43	Accept
Female Business Educators	91	3.51	0.65				

Table 2 shows that at 187 degrees of freedom, the p-value is 0.43 which exceeds the predetermined significance level of 0.05 ($p > 0.05$) This indicates that there is no significant difference between the mean

responses of male and female business educators on Search Engine Marketing (SEM) skills required by university Business Education students in South-South, Nigeria for Self-Employment.

Table 3: Respondents' mean ratings on the level of email marketing skills required by university Business Education students in South-South Nigeria for self-employment

S/N	Item Statements	Male Educators N ₁ =98		X ₂	Female Educators N ₂ = 91		Remark
		X ₁	SD ₁		$\frac{X_1 + X_2}{2}$	SD ₂	
1.	Ability to compose and send email to customers	3.53	0.66	3.64	3.59	0.59	VHR
2.	Ability to create engaging email content	3.36	0.75	3.56	3.46	0.64	HR
3.	Ability to build email lists effectively	3.42	0.77	3.62	3.52	0.66	VHR
4.	Ability to automate email and sequence creation	3.36	0.85	3.48	3.42	0.62	HR
5.	Knowledge of email marketing compliance and regulations	3.28	0.73	3.36	3.32	0.72	HR
6.	Ability to segment audiences and personalize email campaigns	3.23	0.83	3.42	3.33	0.67	HR
7.	Ability to Understand email marketing metrics and analytics	3.42	0.76	3.53	3.48	0.78	HR

8.	Ability to Understand email deliverability best practices	3.23	0.79	3.28	3.26	0.68	HR
9.	Ability to manage email marketing platform	3.39	0.77	3.35	3.37	0.75	HR
10.	Ability to integrate email marketing with other digital marketing channels	3.48	0.71	3.52	3.50	0.69	VHR
Cluster Mean		3.37	0.76	3.48	3.43	0.68	HR

The result presented in Table 3 indicates the mean and standard deviation of the responses of both male and female Business Educators on the email marketing skills required in Business Education for Self-Employment in universities in South-South, Nigeria. The mean scores for the 10 items ranged from 3.23 to 3.64, indicating a general acceptance of the items as email marketing skills required in Business Education for Self-Employment in universities in South-South,

Nigeria. Furthermore, the standard deviation values ranged between 0.59 and 0.85, indicating a relatively low dispersion and a high level of agreement among respondents. Based on these findings, it can be inferred that the items in the above table are email marketing skills required in Business Education for Self-Employment in universities in South-South, Nigeria.

Table 4: Summary of t-test results of difference between the mean ratings of male and female business educators on email marketing skills required by university business education students for self-employment

Groups	N	X	SD	Df	t	P-value	Decision
Male Business Educators	98	3.37	0.76	187	1.05	0.29	Accept
Female Business Educators	91	3.48	0.68				

Table 4 shows the t-test analysis of mean responses of male and female Business Educators on the email marketing skills required in Business Education for Self-Employment in universities in South-South, Nigeria. Based on the findings presented in the table, it can be observed that at 187 degrees of freedom, the p-value is 0.29, which is higher than the predetermined significance level of 0.05 for this study. Consequently, the null hypothesis is accepted. This indicates that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female Business Educators on the email marketing skills required in Business Education for Self-Employment in universities in South-South, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Findings of this study revealed that various Search Engine marketing (SEM) skills are required by university Business Education students in South-South, Nigeria for self-employment. The finding agrees with Olatunde (2023) who reported that Business Educators perceived electronic communication and search engine marketing skills as needed by Business Education undergraduates to be successful in the digital economy. It was also found that gender did not significantly influence the ratings of the business educators on Search Engine marketing (SEM) skills required by university Business

Education students in South-South, Nigeria for self-employment.

Findings of the study further revealed that several email marketing skills are required by university Business Education students in South-South, Nigeria for self-employment. This finding aligns with that of Ambuli, *et al.* (2024) whose findings revealed that emails usage is very effective among college students whereas accepting emails as a marketing tool is not as effective when compared with the usage of emails for other purposes. The study further found out that there was no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female business educators on the email marketing skills required by university Business Education students in South-South, Nigeria for self-employment. This implies that email marketing skills enhance effective marketing communication which has been widely investigated across various research streams in marketing. It also implies that gender does not play a significant role in determining the email marketing skills required in business education for self-employment in universities in south-south, Nigeria.

Conclusion

This study investigated the perceptions of Business Educators on search engine marketing skills and email marketing skills required by university Business Education students in South-South, Nigeria for self-employment. The findings revealed that the students require a wide range of essential skills in search engine marketing (SEM) and email marketing for success in self-employment. The results showed a consensus among male and female business educators that skills in the two areas are very relevant for self-employment by Business Education students of universities in the area of the study. Based on these

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findings, it was concluded that failure to adequately equip university Business Education students in the area of study with relevant search engine and e-mail marketing skills will continue to deprive them from achieving success in self-employment and becoming self-reliant in the current competitive and technology-driven economy and paucity of paid-employment opportunities.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were proffered:

1. University business educators should engage in professional development programmes like short courses, conferences, seminars and workshops on emerging digital marketing tools and techniques to stay current and effectively inculcate the skills in students.
2. Management of universities in the area should sponsor business educators for professional development programmes and partner with digital marketing firms and professionals in order to expose business educators and students to internships and real-world hands-on experiences for enhanced skills acquisition.
3. Curriculum planners should integrate the digital marketing skill components such as search engine marketing (SEM) and email marketing skills with provision for effective implementation in Business Education curriculum at university level in order to adequately equip the students for success in self-employment after graduation.
4. The government should provide adequate ICT infrastructure in Business Education departments to facilitate practical learning and skills development in digital marketing.

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